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The Effect of Audit Report Lag, Leverage Ratio and Audit Tenure On Going Concern Audit Opinion: Empirical Study of Go Public Companies Listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2018-2020

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Abstract

Purpose: The aim of this research is to determine the audit report lag, leverage ratio and audit tenure on going-concern and appropriate audit opinions on go public companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX). **Design/methodology/approach:** Method of research used in this research is the exposure of facts on testing the application of audit report lag, audit tenure and leverage ratio on going concern audit opinion. **Findings:** The outcome of the research indicates that audit report lag and audit tenure have a significant positive effect on going concern audit opinion, but the leverage ratio has insignificant effect on going concern audit opinion. **Practical implications:** The consequences of these going concern audit opinion make distrust of stakeholders, so the going concern audit opinion needs to be minimized in order for all companies to be trusted in financial statement reports. **Originality/value:** Empirical Study on all go public companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2018-2020.

Keywords: Audit Report Lag, Leverage Ratio, Audit Tenure, Audit Opinion - Going Concern

1. Introduction

Financial statements are one of the data and information for owners to see management's performance financially, but owners need an independent party in evaluating the data presented in financial reports. This independent party is what we know as an independent auditor. The independent auditor provides an independent opinion on the company's financial statements to conclude whether there is a material uncertainty about the entity's ability to continue as a going concern and also evaluate whether there is substantial doubt about the entity's ability to continue as a going concern within an appropriate period of time. The auditor acts as a

mediator between management and owners and helps provide reasonable assurance on the financial statements that have been prepared by management.

Much research has been carried out, but the results of the research are very diverse. The results of the research conducted by Putri and Yuyetta (2021) audit report lag have a positive effect on going concern audit opinions, while the findings of research conducted by Mariana et al. (2018) audit report lag have a negative effect on going concern audit opinions. Research conducted by Simanjuntak et al. (2020) leverage ratio has a positive effect on going concern audit opinion, conversely the findings of research by Nugroho et al. (2018) leverage ratio variable has a negative effect on going concern audit opinion. Research conducted by Hasanuddin and Anwar (2019) tenure audits have a positive effect on acceptance of going concern audit opinions, but in the findings of research conducted by Oktaviani and Challen (2020) tenure audit variables have a negative effect on going concern audit opinions.

Going concern audit opinions is interesting to study because previous studies until now have used internal factor and external factor of the corporate. In this research we used audit report lag, leverage ratio, audit tenure as variable independent. Based on the phenomenon in table 1 audit opinions with going concern indicate that there are several problems in financial performance in public companies on the Indonesian Stock Exchange.

Table 1: Companies that have going concern audit opinions

NO	CODE	CORPORATION	AUDIT	OPINION	GOING
			2020	2019	2018
1	BTEL	PT Bakrie Telecom Tbk	√	√	√
2	DWGL	PT Dwi Guna Laksana Tbk	√	√	√
3	DSFI	PT Dharma Samudera Fishing Ind. Tbk	√	√	√
4	ENRG	PT Energi Mega Persada Tbk	√	√	√
5	ESSA	PT Surya Esa Perkasa Tbk	√	√	√
6	GLOB	PT Global Teleshop Tbk	√	√	√
7	IKAI	PT Intikeramik Alamasri Industri Tbk	√	√	√
8	INTA	PT Intraco Penta Tbk	√	√	√
9	LMPI	PT Langgeng Makmur Industri Tbk	√	√	√
10	MITI	PT Mitra Investindo Tbk	√	√	√
11	MTFN	PT Capitalinc Investment Tbk	√	√	√
12	POLY	PT Asia Pacific Fibers Tbk	√	√	√
13	PSKT	PT Red Planet Indonesia Tbk	√	√	√
14	SATU	PT Kota Satu Properti Tbk	√	√	√
15	SSTM	PT Sunson Textile Manufacturer Tbk	√	√	√
16	SULI	PT SLJ Global Tbk	√	√	√
17	TRIO	PT Trikonsel Oke Tbk	√	√	√

Source: www.idx.co.id, reprocessed

Based on the background of the problem in the previous paragraph, the researcher is interested in conducting research on the the factors that influence the going concern audit opinion in public companies in Indonesia in 2018 – 2020.

Research questions are as follows: a.) Does the audit report lag have an influence on the going concern audit opinion? b.) Does the leverage ratio have an influence on the going concern audit opinion? and c.) Does the tenure audit have an influence on the going concern audit opinion?

Research objectives to find out: a.) The effect of audit report lag on going concern audit opinion in companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange, b) The Effect of leverage ratio on going concern audit opinion in

companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange, c) The Effect of audits tenure on going concern audit opinion in companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange.

2. Theoretical Framework and Hypothesis Development

2.1. Theoretical Framework

2.1.1. Agency Theory

According to Agency Theory, the company is seen as a contract between management (as agent) and owner (as principal). Based on this theory, the original human characteristics will prioritize their own interests, management does not always act in the best interests of the owner, so management will tend to carry out profit engineering (earnings management). The misalignment of the agent's and principal's goals is a cost of the agency relationship. The sacrifices that arise from the agency relationship are called agency costs. (Jensen & Meckling, 1976)

Agency relationships also cause information asymmetry. Information asymmetry that occurs between the owner (principal) and management will encourage earnings management. Management will manipulate the information to be presented to the owner because of conflicts of interest and information asymmetry. There are two types of information asymmetry, adverse selection and moral hazard (Scott, 2003). Adverse selection, management has more information than the owner about the company's prospects. Moral hazard, the owner does not know the activities carried out by the management.

2.1.2. Going Concern Audit Opinion

Going concern audit opinion is a modified audit opinion given by the auditor when there is doubt about the company's going concern ability or there is significant uncertainty over the company's viability in carrying out its operations (SPAP, 2011).

Auditing Standard (SA) 570 (IAPI, 2013:3) states that the auditor is responsible for obtaining sufficient and appropriate audit evidence regarding the appropriate use of the going concern assumption by management in preparing and presenting financial statements, and for concluding whether there is a material uncertainty about entity's ability to continue as a going concern. The auditor should consider whether there are events or conditions that are indicated to cast significant doubt on the entity's ability to continue as a going concern in the future. Whether these conditions or events are significant or not will depend on the circumstances, and some of them may only become significant if viewed together with other conditions or events.

Based on Auditing Standard (SA) 570 (IAPI 2013, SA 570: A2). The following are examples of events or conditions that may cast significant doubt about the going concern assumption: (1). Financial - for example, a net liability or net current liability position, a loan with a fixed repayment term nearing its maturity date without realistic prospects of renewal or redemption; or excessive reliance on short-term loans to fund long-term assets, negative operating cash flow, as indicated by historical or prospective financial reports, poor primary financial ratios, inability to repay creditors on due dates. (2). Operations - for example, management's intent to liquidate the entity or to cease operations, loss of key management without replacement, loss of a key market, key customer, franchise, license, or key supplier, labor difficulties, shortage of supplies of goods/materials, and the emergence of highly successful competitors, and (3). Others - for example, non-compliance with capital provisions or other statutory provisions, legal cases faced by the entity which, if successful, could result in claims against the entity that are unlikely to be fulfilled by the entity, changes in laws and regulations or government policies that are expected will have an adverse impact on the entity, and damage to assets caused by uninsured or underinsured natural disasters. Based on diagram below explained in detail ISA 570 revised.

2.1.3. Audit Report Lag

Audit Report Lag is the time span for completion of the financial statement audit as measured by the length of days needed to obtain the independent auditor's report from the closing date of the book to the date stated in the independent auditor's report (Dura and Nuryatno, 2015). (Wiguna, 2012) defines audit lag as the period of time in completing the audit until it is ready for publication

2.1.4. Leverage Ratio

Leverage is a ratio to measure a company's potential to settle all of its obligations (Utamiet et al. 2017). The performance of a company can be viewed through the leverage ratio, high leverage gives a signal that the company is on the verge of bankruptcy (Utami et al 2017). A company that has sufficient wealth or assets to finance all of its obligations or debts is referred to as a solvable company. But on the contrary, when a company does not have sufficient wealth or assets to pay its obligations or debts, then the company is an insolvable company (Yuliyani and Erawati, 2017).

Based on the discussion above, so that leverage is the ratio used to measure how company assets are financed using debt originating from creditors and measures the ability of a company to fulfill all of its financial obligations if the company is to be liquidated.

The leverage ratio can be measured using the Debt to Equity Ratio (DER). The calculation of leverage uses the Debt to Equity Ratio scale with the following formula:

$$\text{Debt to Equity Ratio (DER)} = \text{Total Debt} / \text{Total Equity} \times 100\%.$$

2.1.5. Audit Tenure

Audit tenure is the number of years in which the Public Accountant Firm conducts audit engagements with the same client. When a Public Accounting Firm has a long term relationship with its client, it encourages a better understanding of the client so that the auditor can be more sensitive with regard to the company's going concern issues.

Audit tenure is defined as the length of relationship or engagement between the auditor and his client as measured by the number of years (Arsianto and Rahardjo 2013). A long audit engagement will make the auditor

lose his independence, so that the possibility of giving a going concern audit opinion will be difficult (Ulya 2012).

2.2. Hypothesis Development

2.2.1. Effect of Audit Report Lag on Going Concern Audit Opinion.

Research results by Widastri (2017) found that audit lag has a positive effect on going concern audit opinion. This research is reinforced by research by Imani et al (2017) which shows that audit lag has a positive effect on going concern audit opinion..

Hypothesis one: Audit Report Lag affects Going Concern Audit Opinion.

2.2.2. Effect of Leverage Ratio on Going Concern Audit Opinion.

Research by Aryantika and Rasmini's (2016), Pasaribu (2015) stated that leverage has a positive effect on going concern audit opinion. research by Aryantika and Rasmini (2016), Pasaribu (2015) the leverage ratio variable has a positive effect on going concern audit opinion. The greater the debt ratio of a company, the debt owned by a company will be even greater, so that the risk of failure of a company in paying its obligations or debts is higher. This makes the company more likely to get a going concern audit opinion.

Hypothesis two: Leverage Ratio affects Going Concern Audit Opinion

2.2.3. Effect of Audit Tenure on Going Concern Audit Opinion.

Research by Arsianto and Rahardjo's (2013) shows the results that Audit Tenure have a negative effect on going concern audit opinion. Research by Damanhuri and Putra (2020) Audit Tenure has a negative effect on going concern audit opinion. Yanuariska and Ardiati (2018), Saputra and Kustina (2018), Widya (2017), Krissindiastuti and Rasmini (2016), Nursasi and Maria (2015) show that Audit Tenure have a negative effect on going concern audit opinion..

Hypothesis three: Audit Tenure affects Going Concern Audit Opinion

3. Method

The research population is all companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) from 2018 to 2020. The research sample consists of 44 companies listed with three years of observation. Total sample of this study amounted to 108. Data collection techniques using secondary data obtained from the sample company websites and audited financial reports that have been published on the IDX website and then processed or calculated to obtain research variables determined according to the background of the research problem, research questions, and research objectives to be realized. The data collected from secondary data is tabulated, then it will be processed using *Eviews* 10.0.

Table 2: Operational Variable Definition

Variable	Indicator	Measurement
Audit report lag (Liwe et.al 2018)	ARL=Audit report date – FS date	Nominal
Leverage ratio (Zhou et al.,2018).	Debt to Equity Ratio	Ratio
Audit tenure. (Arsianto and Rahardjo 2013)	the length of the KAP relationship with the client company	Interval
going concern audit opinion ((SA 570 R 2012)	1 = for auditees who receive a going concern audit opinion (GCAO). 0 = for auditees who receive non-going concern audit opinions (NGCAO).	Nominal

The statistical tool used for evaluating and interpreting the secondary data into meaningful information for resulting analysis is *Eviews 10.0*. Panel Data Estimation Method: the panel data regression analysis method aims to obtain an overview of the relationship between one variable and another. Panel data uses many companies and takes several years. There are three models used for panel data regression: common effect, fixed effect, and random effect.

Panel Data Regression Model Selection, Chow test testing to select the best approach between the Common Effect Model (CEM) and Fixed Effect Model (FEM) approaches that are most appropriate to use in estimating panel data. The Hausman test is used to determine whether a panel data model is better off using the Fixed Effect Model (FEM) or Random Effect Model (REM). The Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test is used to compare which model is the most appropriate between the Common Effect Model (CEM) or the Random Effect Model (REM).

The regression model developed to test the hypotheses that have been formulated in this study are:

$$\text{OAGC} = \alpha + \beta_1\text{ARL} + \beta_2\text{LEV} + \beta_3\text{AT} + \epsilon$$

4. Findings and Discussion

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics Results

	OAGC	C	ARL	LEV	AT
Median	1.00	1.00	87.00	1.00	2.00
Maximum	1.00	1.00	272.00	57.15	3.00
Minimum	0.00	1.00	11.00	-39.32	1.00
Std. Dev.	0.40	0.00	38.14	10.31	0.78

Source: *Eviews versi 10.0*

The going concern audit opinion variable has an average value of 0.79, a median value of 1.00 and a standard deviation of 0.40. The maximum value is 1.00 and the minimum value is 0.00.

The audit report lag variable has an average value of 97.91, a median value of 87.00 and a standard deviation of 38.14. The maximum value of 272.00 is owned by PT Trikonsel Oke Tbk in 2019. The minimum value is 11.00 owned by PT Dwi Guna Laksana Tbk in 2018.

The leverage variable has an average value of 2.25, a median value of 1.00 and a standard deviation of 10.31. The maximum value of 57.15 is owned by PT Capitalinc Investment Tbk in 2019. The minimum value is -39.32 owned by PT Capitalinc Investment Tbk in 2020.

The tenure audit variable has an average value of 1.77, a median value of 2.00 and a standard deviation of 0.78. The maximum value is 3.00. Minimum value 1.00.

4.1. Hypothesis testing

Based on the results of the Chow-test showed that the Fixed Effect model was selected. On the other hand, the results of the Hausman model test show that the Fixed Effect model is selected. These results prove that the selected panel model is Fixed Effect.

Table 4: Logistic Regression Results

Dependent Variable: OAGC
 Method: ML - Binary Logit (Newton-Raphson /
 Marquardt steps)
 Sample: 1 132
 Included observations: 132

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
C	2.98	1.03	2.88	0.003
ARL	0.02	0.00	2.69	0.007
LEV	-0.01	0.02	-0.37	0.707
AT	1.28	0.39	3.26	0.001

Source: Eviews 10.0

Based on the results of the panel data regression test in table 5, the panel data regression equation is obtained as follows:

$$\text{OAGC} = 2.98 + 0.02 \text{ ARL} - 0.01 \text{ LEV} + 1.28 \text{ AT} + \epsilon$$

Based on table 4 that audit report lag has a significant positive effect on going concern audit opinion. The results of the t test show that the audit report lag variable obtains a z-statistic value greater than t table ($2.69 > 1.98$) and a probability smaller than the significance value ($0.0070 < 0.05$), so it can be concluded that hypothesis one is accepted or there is significant effect between variable audit report lag with going concern audit opinion.

Based on table table 4 that leverage has no significant effect on going concern audit opinion. The results of the t test show that leverage obtains a z statistical value that is smaller than t table ($-0.37 < 1.98$) and the probability is greater than the significance value ($0.7078 > 0.05$), so it can be concluded that hypothesis two is rejected or the variable leverage has no effect on going concern audit opinion

Based on table 4, that audit tenure has a significant positive effect on going concern audit opinion. The results of the t test show that the audit report lag variable obtains a z statistic value that is greater than t table ($3.26 > 1.98$) and the probability is smaller than the significance value ($0.0011 < 0.05$), so it can be concluded that hypothesis three is accepted or there is a significant effect between tenure audit variables and going concern audit opinion.

Table 5: Determination Coefficient Test Results (Mc Fadden R Square)

McFadden R-squared	0.689	Mean dependent var	0.795
S.D. dependent var	0.704	S.E. of regression	0.365

Source: Eviews 10.0

Based on table 5 states that the Adjusted R-squared value is 0.68, meaning that the magnitude of the coefficient of determination in this study is 0.68. This means that the independent variable is able to explain the dependent variable only 68.0% and the remaining 42.0% is influenced by other independent variables. not investigated in this study.

5. Discussion

5.1. The Effect of Audit Report Lag on Going Concern Audit Opinion.

The results show that audit report lag has a significant positive effect on going concern audit opinion. This indicates that the longer the audit report lag, the going concern audit opinion will increase. The results of this study are in line with the results of research by Utama & Badera (2016) which revealed that audit report lag has a significant positive effect on acceptance of going concern audit opinions..

5.2. The Effect of Leverage Ratio on Going Concern Audit Opinion.

The results of the analysis state that the variable leverage has a negative effect on going concern audit opinion insignificant. This indicates that the greater the leverage ratio, the less likely it is to receive a going concern audit opinion. The results support the statements made from previous research by Kusumaningrum and Zulaikha (2019) which state that leverage has no significant effect on going concern audit opinions.

5.3. The Effect of Audit Tenure on Going Concern Audit Opinion.

The results of the analysis state that tenure audit has a significant positive effect on going concern audit opinion. This indicates that the longer the audit tenure, the go-in-concern audit opinion will increase. Research conducted by Syahputra and Yahya (2017) has research results that are in line with stating that tenure audits have a significant positive effect on going concern audit opinion.

6. Conclusion

The results show that Audit report lag has a significant positive effect on going concern audit opinion. Leverage has no effect on going concern audit opinion. The tenure audit has a significant positive effect on the going concern audit opinion.

The limitations that exist in this study are as follows: The research sample used was only 44 companies so that the data obtained was limited. The research period used in this study is only 3 years, namely 2018-2020. The leverage ratio variable has no significant effect, this is different from previous researchers who stated leverage had a significant positive effect on going concern audit opinion.

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